

A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Structure Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Pneumonia and its Prevention among Staff Nurses in Selected Hospitals at Vijayapura, Karnataka

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Abstract: Background: The children, geriatric people and some people already having health problems they are risk group to get pneumonia. In this period care is very essential. The paediatric care is more important. The neonates are at risk for various health problems even though they born with average birth weight. Neonatal health problems are sepsis, birth asphyxia, hypothermia, hyperthermia, inability to suck breast milk, jaundice, difficulty to urination and defecation etc. Most of the health problems are life threatening to the people especially pneumonia also. They need optimal care for their improved survival. **Objectives:** (1) To assess the knowledge of staff nurses in selected hospital on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention. (2) To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention. (3) To find out the association between post-tests knowledge scores of staff nurses on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention and with their selected socio-demographic variables. **Methodology:** The research design used for this study is quasi experimental (one group pretest) design. The independent variable is the structured questionnaire and the dependent variable is knowledge of the staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention. In order to achieve the objective of the present study, quasi experimental one group pretest, posttest with an evaluative approach was adopted. The sample was selected by purposive sampling technique. The sample comprised of 60 staff nurses and data were collected before and after administration of structured teaching programme. **Results:** Reveals that in the pretest, majority of subjects 47(78.33%) had average knowledge, 08 (13.33%) had good knowledge and 5 (8.33%) had poor knowledge. It reveals that the mean percentage of knowledge scored was (26.66%). Reveals that the percentage of knowledge scores in introduction and definition about pneumonia and its prevention was (100%), incidence of pneumonia was (40%), types of pneumonia was (40%), causes and risk factors was (50%), signs and symptoms was (100%) and diagnostic evaluation was (66.6%), management of pneumonia was (44.4%) and prevention of pneumonia was (33.3%). **Interpretation and conclusion:** The findings of this study reveal that the structured teaching programme will increase the knowledge of the staff nurses on pneumonia and its prevention. Findings of the study shows that knowledge of the staff nurses, percentage of knowledge scores in introduction and definition about pneumonia and its prevention was (100%), incidence of pneumonia was (40%), types of pneumonia was (40%), causes and risk factors was (50%), signs and symptoms was (100%) and diagnostic evaluation was (66.6%), management of pneumonia was (44.4%) and prevention of pneumonia was (33.3%).

Keywords: Effectiveness, Structured Teaching Programme, Knowledge, Pneumonia, Staff Nurses.

Introduction

The use of artificial airway and mechanical ventilation (MV) is essential and common life-saving measure in the intensive care unit (ICU) because 76% of ICU patients require ventilator support. However, MV carries many risks and complications, the most common one being ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) [1]. Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is the most common infectious complication among the patients admitted in the intensive care units (ICUs), which is developed in the patients receiving mechanical ventilation; it is developing within 48 to 72 hours after the intubation of the tracheal tube [2]. The incidence of VAP is 37.2 per 1000 ventilation day in developing countries and the mortality rate for VAP patients was 80% [3]. VAP is also associated with considerable morbidity, including prolonged ICU length of stay, prolonged mechanical ventilation, and increased costs of hospitalization [4, 5, 6]. Hence early detection of problems and initiation of prompt management are the important responsibilities of staff nurses. Staff nurses should be adequately educated about pneumonia and its prevention.

Methodology

The research design used for this study is quasi experimental (one group pretest) design. The independent variable is the structured questionnaire and the dependent variable is knowledge of the staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention. This chapter describes the methodology followed to assess the knowledge scores of pneumonia and its prevention among staff nurses in selected hospitals Vijayapura. The tool used for the study is self-administered knowledge Questionnaire to assess the knowledge of the staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention. Content validity of the tool is given by experts and tool is found to be reliable and feasible. Structured teaching programme is prepared to enhance the knowledge about pneumonia and its prevention among staff nurses and is validated by the experts before administration. The main study was conducted for 1 week at Ashwini's Bidari Hospital, Vijayapura. Pretest was done to the staff nurses and assessed their knowledge.

Results

"There is nothing exhilarating than to be shot at without result".-Winston Churchill.

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data collected from 60 staff nurses in selected hospital, Vijayapura regarding pneumonia and its prevention by using a structured knowledge questionnaire. Analysis is the process of organizing and synthesizing the data in such a way that research questions can be answered and hypotheses is tested. The purpose of the analysis is to reduce the data in an intelligible and interpretable form, so that the relation of research problem can be studied and tested. The purpose of the data analysis is to translate the information collected during the course of the study into interpretable form so that the research question could be answered. Data gathered were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The analysis of the data of the present study has been organized in relation to the objectives and hypotheses of the study.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To assess the knowledge of staff nurses in selected hospital on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention.
- 2) To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention.
- 3) To find out the association between post-tests knowledge scores of staff nurses on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention and with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Presentation of the data

The data is presented under the following sections:

Section I: Description of socio-demographic characteristics of the samples.

Section II: Assessment of knowledge of staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Section III: Assessment of effectiveness of structured teaching programme on pneumonia and its prevention among staff nurses in the selected hospitals, at Vijayapura. Which is further categorized in to 4 parts:

Part 1: Comparison of knowledge level of staff nurses in the pretest and posttest.

Part 2: Area wise effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention among staff nurses in the selected hospitals, at vijayapura.

Part 3: Testing Hypothesis.

Part 4: Association between knowledge score of staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Section I: Distribution of subject characteristics according to socio-demographic variables.

This section describes the characteristics of mother in terms of age, Gender, educational status, Experience, place of residence and source of information.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to socio-demographic variables

S. No.	Socio-demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Age (in years)		
	a) 22-27	47	78.33%
	b) 28-33	10	16.66%
	c) 34-39	2	3.33%
	d) 40-45	1	1.66%
2	Gender		
	a) Male	30	50%
	b) Female	30	50%
3	Educational status		
	a) GNM Nursing	45	75%
	b) B.Sc. Nursing	5	8.33%
	c) PB. B.Sc. Nursing	8	13.33%
	d) M.Sc. Nursing	2	3.33%
4	Experience (in years)		
	a) 1-4	49	81.66%
	b) 5-9	9	15%
	c) 10-14	2	3.33%
	d) More than 14	0	0%
5	Place of residence		
	a) Urban	32	53.33%
	b) Rural	28	46.66%
6	Sources of information		
	a) Books and Magazines	35	58.33%
	b) Internet	12	20%
	c) News paper	7	11.66%
	d) Friends	5	8.33%

Maximum subjects i.e., 47(78.33%) were in the age group of 22-27 years, 10(16.66%) were in the age group of 28-33 years, 2(3.33%) were in the age group of 34-39 years and 1(1.66%) of them were in the age group of 40-45 years.

Subjects are equal in gender i.e., 30(50%) were male, 30(50%) were female.

Maximum subjects 50(75%) were GNM Nursing, 5(8.33%) were B.Sc. Nursing, 8(13.33%) were PB. B.Sc. Nursing and 2(3.33%) were M.Sc. completed.

Maximum subjects i.e., 49(81.66%) were has 1-4 year experience, 9(15%) were 5-9 year, 2(3.33%) were 10-14 year of experience.

Maximum subjects are in Urban i.e., 32(55.33%) and Rural 28(46.66%).

Maximum subjects i.e., 36(58.33%) were used Books, 12(20%) were used Internet, 7(11.66%) were used Newspaper and 5(8.33%) were used source of information as a friends group.

Section 1: Description of socio-demographic characteristics of samples

Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to their age group reveals that out of 60 subjects, the percentage (78.33%) of 47 subjects were belongs to the age group of 22-27 years, whereas 10(16.6%) of were belongs to 28-33 years, 2(3.33%) of were belongs to 34-35 years and 1(1.66%) subjects were belongs to 40-45 years.

Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to their Gender reveals that out of 60 subjects, the percentage (50%) of 30 subjects were belongs to male gender and also (50%) of 30 subjects were belongs to Female gender.

Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to their age group reveals that out of 60 subjects, the percentage (75%) of 45 subjects were belongs to GNM Nursing, whereas 5 (8.33%) of were belongs to B.Sc. Nursing, 8(13.33%) of were belongs to PB. B.Sc. Nursing and 2(3.33%) subjects were belongs to M.Sc. Nursing.

Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to their age group reveals that out of 60 subjects, the percentage (81.66%) of 49 subjects were belongs to Experience of 1-4 year, whereas 9(15%) of were belongs to 5-9 year, 2(3.33%) of were belongs to 10-14 year of experience and no one is having more than 14 year of experience.

Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to their Gender reveals that out of 60 subjects, the percentage (53.33%) of 32 subjects were belongs to Urban are and (46.66%) of 28 subjects were belongs to Rural area.

Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to their age group reveals that out of 60 subjects, the percentage (58.33%) of 36 subjects were belongs to Books, whereas 12(20%) of were belongs to Internet sources, 7(11.66%) of were belongs to Newspaper and 5 (8.33%) subjects were belongs to Friends group.

Section II: Analysis and interpretation of knowledge of staff nurse regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Table 2. Knowledge of staff nurse regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Test	Level of knowledge	Range of score	No. Members	Percentage %
Pre-test	Very good	25-30	-	0%
	Good	19-24	8	13.33%
	Average	13-18	47	78.33%
	Poor	7-12	5	8.33%
	Very poor	0-6	0	0%
				60

Percentage wise distribution of subjects in pretest reveals that out of 60 subjects, the highest percentage (78.33) of staff nurses have poor knowledge and no one had got very good and good knowledge. Hence it reveals that majority of staff nurses have poor knowledge.

Section III: Assessment of effectiveness of structured teaching programme on pneumonia and its prevention among staff nurses in the selected hospitals, at vijayapura. Which is further categorized in to 4 parts:

Part I: Comparison of knowledge level of staff nurses in the pretest and post test

Table 3. Comparison of knowledge level of staff nurses in the pretest and post test

Level of knowledge	Range of scores	Pretest O ₁		Post test	
		Number of respondents	Percentage	Number of respondents	Percentage
Very poor	0-6	0	0%	-	0%
Poor	7-12	5	8.33%	-	0%
Average	13-18	47	78.33%	1	1.66%
Good	19-24	8	13.333%	18	30%
Very good	25-30	-	0%	41	68.333%
Total		60	100%	60	100%

The knowledge wise comparison of subjects in pretest and posttest reveals that the following results. In pretest, out of 60 subjects, the highest percentage (78.33%) of staff nurses had average knowledge whereas lowest percentage (8.33%) of staff nurses were with poor knowledge, (13.33%) staff nurses had good knowledge and no one had got very good knowledge. Hence it reveals that majority (78.33%) of staff nurses had average knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention. However after STP (posttest) the higher percentage (68.333%) of staff nurses with very good knowledge, (30%) staff nurses had good knowledge, (1.66%) staff nurses had average knowledge and no one had poor and very poor knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Part 2: Area wise effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Table 4. Area wise mean, standard deviation, and mean percentage of knowledge scores in pretest and posttest.

Knowledge Area	Max score	Pre-Test (o ₁)		Post-Test (o ₂)		Effectiveness	
		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Knowledge regarding introduction and definition of pneumonia	3	2.9±0.04	100	3±0	0	0.1±0.04	100
Knowledge regarding incidence of pneumonia	2	0.6±0.5	50	0.9±0.83	50	0.3±0.33	0
Knowledge regarding types pneumonia	5	1.95±0.9	40	5±0.5	100	3.05±0.4	60
Knowledge regarding causes and risk factors of pneumonia	4	2.1±0.8	50	3.6±0.66	100	1.5±0.14	50
Knowledge regarding signs and symptoms of pneumonia	1	0.6±0.5	100	0.8±0.38	100	0.2±0.12	0

Knowledge regarding diagnostic evaluation of pneumonia	3	1.7±0.8	66.6	2.7±0.58	100	1±0.22	33.4
Knowledge regarding management of pneumonia	9	4.4±1.5	44.4	8.1±1.15	88.8	3.7±0.35	44.4
Knowledge regarding prevention of pneumonia	3	1.4±0.7	33.3	1.9±0.9	66.6	0.5±0.2	33.3
Total	30	15.65±5.74	484.3	26±5	605.4	10.35±1.8	232.2

Area wise comparison of mean and standard deviation of the knowledge scores of the pretest and posttest reveals an increase in the mean knowledge score of the staff nurses after STP.

Comparison of area wise mean and standard deviation of the knowledge scores in the area of knowledge regarding introduction and definition shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (2.9) with SD (± 1.2) with mean percentage (100%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in the area was (3) with SD (± 0) with mean percentage (0%) of total score. In the area wise knowledge regarding incidence shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (0.6) with SD (± 0.5) with mean percentage (50%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (0.9) with SD (± 0.83) with mean percentage (50%) of total score. In the area wise knowledge regarding types shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (1.95) with SD (± 0.9) with mean percentage (40%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (5) with SD (± 0.5) with mean percentage (100%) of total score.

In the area wise knowledge regarding causes and risk factors shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (2.1) with SD (± 0.8) with mean percentage (50%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (3.6) with SD (± 0.66) with mean percentage (100%) of total score. In the area wise knowledge regarding signs and symptoms shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (0.6) with SD (± 0.5) with mean percentage (100%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (0.8) with SD (± 0.38) with mean percentage (100%) of total score. In the area wise knowledge regarding diagnostic evaluation shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (1.7) with SD (± 0.8) with mean percentage (66.6%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (2.7) with SD (± 0.58) with mean percentage (100%) of total score.

In the area wise knowledge regarding management shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (4.4) with SD (± 1.5) with mean percentage (44.4%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (8.1) with SD (± 1.15) with mean percentage (88.8%) of total score. In the area wise knowledge regarding prevention shows that the pretest mean knowledge score was (1.4) with SD (± 0.7) with mean percentage (33.3%) of total score whereas the posttest mean of knowledge score in this area was (1.9) with SD (± 0.9) with mean percentage (66.6%) of total score.

In overall findings reveals that the posttest knowledge scores was more than (26 ± 5) when compared to pretest knowledge score (15.65 ± 5.74). Hence it indicates that the STP was effective in enhancing the knowledge of staff nurses.

Part 3: Testing Hypothesis

To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme, research hypothesis is formulated.

H₁: There will be significant difference between the pre-test knowledge and post-test knowledge scores of staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Table 5. Significant difference between the pre-test knowledge and post-test knowledge scores of staff nurses.

Test	Mean	Mean difference	SD Error	Paired 't' value	Table value
Pretest (O ₁)	15.9	10	1.1	70.3	1.96
Posttest (O ₂)	25.7				

As the calculated 't' value 70.3 was much higher than table 't' value (1.96) the hypothesis: **H₁**- there will be significant difference between pretest knowledge and posttest knowledge scores of staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention is accepted. Findings revealed the presence of significant difference between pretest and posttest knowledge scores. Hence the structured teaching programme is proved to be effective.

Part 4: Association between knowledge score of staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Table 6. Association between posttest knowledge scores selected socio-demographic variables.

S. No	Socio-demographic variables	df	Chi-square value	Table value	Level of significance	Association
1	Age	1	0.1099	3.84	0.05	Not significant
2	Gender	1	1.4222	3.84	0.05	Not significant
3	Educational status	1	1.7584	3.84	0.05	Not significant
4	Experience	1	1.4588	3.84	0.05	Not significant
5	Place of residence	1	0.3497	3.84	0.05	Not significant
6	Sources of information	1	2.3148	3.84	0.05	Not significant

Chi square test was used to find the association between the socio-demographic variables and knowledge of subjects regarding pneumonia and its prevention. No significant association was found between the knowledge of pneumonia and its prevention and their socio-demographic variables: age, gender, educational status, experience, place of residence, sources of information.

Significant association was found between the knowledge of pneumonia and its prevention and their socio-demographic variables: age, gender, educational status, experience, place of residence, sources of information.

Summary

This chapter dealt with the analysis and interpretation of the findings of the study. The data gathered were summarized in the master sheet and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. In overall findings reveals that the posttest knowledge scores was more than (26±5) when compared to pretest knowledge score (15.65±5.74). Hence it indicates that the STP was effective in enhancing the knowledge of staff nurses.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Sedwick MB, Lance-Smith M, Reeder SJ, Nardi J. Using evidence-based practice to prevent ventilator-associated pneumonia. Crit Care Nurs. 2012 Aug 1;32(4):41-51.
2. Timsit JF, Zahar JR, Chevret S. Attributable mortality of ventilator-associated pneumonia. Current opinion in critical care. 2011 Oct 1;17(5):464-71.

3. Alp E, Kalin G, Coskun R, Sungur M, Guven M, Doganay M. Economic burden of entilator-associated pneumonia in a developing country. *J Hosp Infect.* 2012 Jun 1;81(2):128-30.
4. Heyland DK, Cook DJ, Griffith L, Keenan SP, Brun-Buisson C. The attributable morbidity and mortality of ventilator-associated pneumonia in the critically ill patient. *American J Resp Crit Care Med.* 1999 Apr 1;159(4):1249-56.
5. Luna CM, Blanzaco D, Niederman MS, Matarucco W, Baredes NC, Desmery P, Palizas F, Menga G, Rios F, Apezteguia C. Resolution of ventilator-associated pneumonia: prospective evaluation of the clinical pulmonary infection score as an early clinical predictor of outcome. *Crit Care Med.* 2003 Mar 1;31(3):676-82.
6. Rello J, Ollendorf DA, Oster G, Vera-Llonch M, Bellm L, Redman R, Kollef MH. Epidemiology and outcomes of ventilator-associated pneumonia in a large US database. *Chest.* 2002 Dec 1;122(6):2115-21.

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